

Technical Report: Accuracy of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* capsule serotype predictions from whole genome sequences

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Summary

Klebsiella pneumoniae is a priority pathogen for the development of novel therapeutic and prophylactic measures such as vaccines and monoclonal antibody therapies. Key molecular targets include the polysaccharide capsule, which protects *K. pneumoniae* from phagocytosis and serum bactericidal activity, and is highly immunogenic. A total of 77 distinct serological phenotypes have been defined but more than 160 different capsule polysaccharides are predicted based on analysis of the corresponding capsule (K) biosynthesis loci from whole genome sequences (WGS). These loci form the basis for WGS-based capsule typing with the computational tool, Kaptive, enabling capsule epidemiology investigations at scale to inform vaccine design. However, to-date limited data has been available with which to assess the accuracy of Kaptive for phenotype inference.

Here we present a preliminary analysis of 731 matched serological and genomic K-type calls, and show that 84.5% of the serotypes are concordant with genomic predictions, supporting use of Kaptive for seroepidemiology analyses. Ongoing work will expand the dataset, investigate genotype-phenotype discrepancies and update Kaptive to further improve its accuracy.

Introduction

Klebsiella pneumoniae is an opportunistic pathogen and a leading cause of hospital-acquired infections with growing rates of antimicrobial resistance globally [1]. It is also the leading cause of neonatal sepsis in low- and middle-income countries, where it is associated with high mortality rates [2]. As a consequence the World Health Organization (WHO) defines *K. pneumoniae* as an urgent priority for novel preventative and therapeutic strategies [3], and key target for vaccine development [4]. The recent WHO vaccine value profile highlighted polysaccharide conjugate vaccines as a potential solution, specifically targeting vulnerable adolescent and adult populations, and prevention of neonatal sepsis through maternal vaccination [5]. Notably, it was recently estimated that a vaccine with 70% efficacy administered to pregnant women to protect neonates would prevent almost 400,000 neonatal sepsis cases yearly, and 80,000 neonatal deaths [6].

Members of the *K. pneumoniae* species complex (KpSC, *K. pneumoniae* and closely related species; *Klebsiella variicola*, *Klebsiella quasipneumoniae*, *Klebsiella quasivariicola* and *Klebsiella africana* [7]) express two antigenic surface polysaccharides, the capsular polysaccharide or K antigen, and the outer lipopolysaccharide or O antigen, both of which have been shown to elicit effective immune responses and are considered attractive vaccination targets [5, 8, 9]. As vaccine valency is limited, and K and O antigens are highly diverse in KpSC [2, 10–14], seroepidemiology analyses are essential to prioritise antigens for vaccine development and continued efficacy. However, there are currently no serological typing approaches for KpSC O antigens and the use of serological K typing declined rapidly following the 1970s-80s because the methods are technically challenging, and sera were not widely accessible. Furthermore, 10-70% KpSC isolates were serologically non-typeable or cross-reactive [15–17]. As a consequence, it was not possible to understand population capsule diversity nor epidemiology.

Fortunately, the rapid growth of whole genome sequencing (WGS) has provided new opportunities to explore KpSC K and O antigen diversity at scale. We previously developed

Kaptive, a set of genomic analysis resources to support KpSC K and O seroepidemiology by typing the corresponding K and O polysaccharide synthesis loci [18–21]. Kaptive is freely available as a command-line program and implemented in the user-friendly online Kaptive-Web [19] and Pathogenwatch surveillance platforms [22]. It has been widely adopted by the research and public health communities, and has been used to make inferences about KpSC K and O antigen diversity, epidemiology and evolution [10–14, 23].

Kaptive takes an input genome assembly and reports the best matching K or O locus from a defined reference database. Each distinct locus is defined as a distinct set of sugar synthesis and export genes that are predicted to produce distinct polysaccharide structures [18, 24]. The KpSC K locus database comprises; i) loci corresponding to those in the 77 serotype reference strains (K1-K72, K74 and K79-K82 [24–27]), numbered by the corresponding capsule serotype and prefixed with “KL” (for K-locus, to distinguish between genotype and phenotype; e.g. KL1 <-> K1); plus ii) an additional 86 K loci identified from the WGS of isolates with unknown serotypes [18, 20] (numbered from 100-186 to enable easy distinction from loci associated with known serological types).

We recently updated the Kaptive typing algorithm (released as Kaptive v3) and showed that it identifies KpSC K loci with high accuracy ($\geq 98\%$), on typical Illumina-based draft WGS [21]. However, serological phenotype prediction depends on both accurate locus identification and biological knowledge about the relationship between genotype and phenotype. Unfortunately, to-date there have been very limited matched serotype and WGS data available with which to assess serotype predictive accuracy. At the time of the first Kaptive publication, we were able to source data for 86 isolates from the literature and public databases (excluding the serotype reference strains), of which 77 were successfully typed by Kaptive (89.5%). Among those typeable isolates, 57 (74%) serotypes matched the predicted phenotype [18]. However, we did not have access to any of the isolates for re-testing or re-sequencing.

Here we report a preliminary analysis of 731 newly serotyped isolates with matched WGS typing predictions generated using the latest version of Kaptive (v3). We present a preliminary accuracy estimate and describe ongoing work to investigate instances of genotype-phenotype discordance.

Methods

Bacterial isolates and whole genome sequencing

K. pneumoniae isolate stocks (n=797) were sourced from multiple studies and contributors. Collection methodologies, inclusion criteria and ethical approvals were described in the original study reports:

1. BARNARDS, n=248; neonatal sepsis isolates contributed from seven countries in Africa and South Asia via the Burden of Antimicrobial Resistance in Developing Societies study (BARNARDS [2]).
2. SA-WITS-VIDA, n=292 [28]: Blood and cerebrospinal fluid isolates from infants <90 days old, contributed from an observational study of invasive bacterial disease in South Africa. Plus, post-mortem isolates contributed from the Child Health and Mortality Prevention Study (CHAMPS) and the Mits-lite study at the Soweto, South Africa site [28].

3. MLW, n=257; blood isolates from adults and neonates contributed from a study of invasive *K. pneumoniae* disease in Malawi [13].

Paired-end Illumina sequences were generated by each contributing study as described in the original reports. Briefly, for BARNARDS isolates, DNA was extracted using the QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (Qiagen), sequencing libraries prepared using the Nextera XT V2 kit (Illumina) and sequenced on the Illumina MiSeq platform. For the SA-WITS-VIDA isolates, DNA was extracted using the EasyMag method (bioMérieux), sequencing libraries prepared using the Nextera CD DNA kit (Illumina) and libraries sequenced on the Illumina MiSeq platform. For MLW isolates, DNA was extracted using the QIA Symphony machine and QIA Symphony DSP kit (Qiagen) with onboard lysis, sequencing libraries prepared using Select XT custom library prep kit (Agilent) or NEB UltraII custom kit (New England Biolabs), and sequenced on Illumina HiSeq X10 platform.

Frozen isolate stocks were sent to Statens Serum Institute (Denmark) for serology. Where stocks yielded *Klebsiella* plus one or more other contaminating species and/or *Klebsiella* displaying multiple colony morphology variants, they were re-sequenced locally using the Oxford Nanopore Technologies MinION platform to confirm selected isolate identities: Pure bacteria culture was grown overnight at 35°C on 5% blood agar plate (SSI Diagnostica, Denmark). Overnight bacteria were enzymatically lysed in 1x PBS pH 7.2 (Gibco Life Technologies Limited, UK) added 1:12 proteinase K (Roche, Germany) and incubated at 56°C for 60 min. Lysis extract was used for further DNA extraction and genomic DNA was extracted on a MagNA Pure 96 automated extraction platform using the Viral NA Small Volume DNA Multi-Sample Kit (Roche, Switzerland). The Quant-iT dsDNA BR and HS Assay Kits (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) were used for DNA quantification and fluorescence was measured on a FLUOstar Omega (BMG LabTech, Germany). Sequencing libraries were prepared using the rapid barcoding kit (SQK-RBK114.96; Oxford Nanopore Technologies) according to the manufacturer's protocol, using 200 ng DNA input. The resulting library was loaded on a R10.4.1 Flowcell and sequencing performed via the MinKNOW software on a GridION sequencing instrument.

Whole genome sequence analysis

Illumina sequences were quality filtered and adapters removed with Trim Galore v0.6.7 (github.com/FelixKrueger/TrimGalore), after which they were *de novo* assembled using SPAdes v3.15.3 [29] implemented in Unicycler v0.5.0 [30] with default parameters (BARNARDS and MLW); or sequences were quality filtered and adapters removed with Trim Galore v0.6.2, prior to *de novo* assembly with SPAdes v4.0 and Shovill v1.1.0 (github.com/tseemann/shovill) (SA-WITS-VIDA). Raw ONT reads were basecalled with dorado (v. 7.3.11) on Super High Accuracy setting. Subsequent quality filtering of reads was performed with chopper (v. 0.2.0) [31], retaining reads with Phred Quality score >Q12. Filtered ONT reads were assembled using hybracter v0.11.2 [32].

Assemblies were filtered using the quality control criteria established by the KlebNET-Genomic Surveillance Platform to exclude those with; i) >500 total contigs; ii) total assembly length ≤4,969,898 bp or ≥6,132,846 bp. Kleborate v3.1.3 [12] was used to determine 7-gene multi-locus sequence types (STs) and Kaptive v3.1.0 [21] was used for K locus typing. Pathogenwatch was used to count pairwise single nucleotide variants in 1972 core genes for a subset of isolates (see below) [22].

Capsular serotyping

Capsule serotyping was performed using immunoelectrophoresis (IE) and countercurrent immunoelectrophoresis (CCIE) with K antisera against K antigens (from capsule extract). During electrophoresis, the negatively charged K antigens move against the anode and when in contact with the neutral K antisera, an agglutination is seen as a precipitation in the agarose gel.

Capsule extract was produced from pure bacterial culture incubated in ox-heart broth (SSI Diagnostica, Denmark) overnight at 36°C. The overnight culture was further spread on ox-heart agar plates (SSI Diagnostica, Denmark) and incubated at 36°C overnight followed by an additional incubation at room temperature overnight. All material from the plate was suspended in PBS pH 7,4 (SSI Diagnostica, Denmark) and heat treated at 100°C for 1 hour. After centrifugation, the supernatant was collected as capsule extract.

All strains were initially screened in K antisera pools (SSI Diagnostica, Denmark) using CCIE and positive reactions in pools were followed by a CCIE with selected single sera. A 1,5% Trisricin agarose gel (SSI Diagnostica, Denmark) was used and run at 100V in 50 min. Wells were filled in pairs, with 15 µl K sera above and 15 µl 1:100 K extract diluted in PBS pH 7,4 below. The positive reactions were rated from + (minimal effect) to +++ (maximum and typical effect). A negative result was repeated in CCIE with K extract diluted in PBS pH 7,4 1:200 and 1:400. If still negative results, the presence of capsular polysaccharide was examined using phase-contrast microscopy.

For possible cross reactions, strains were further examined using IE comparing the phenotypic reaction in single sera and absorbed sera against the reaction seen in the corresponding K type reference strain (SSI, Denmark). A 1% Trisricin agarose gel was used for IE and separated wells were filled with K extract from the tested strain and the corresponding K type reference strain and run at 150V for 50 min. After the electrophoresis, a “ditch” separating the two wells with K extract, was filled with K sera and incubated in a moisture chamber overnight at room temperature. The pattern of precipitation was compared and an identical pattern was identified as an identical serological response.

Novel antisera

Novel antisera were produced for genotypes of interest identified from a meta-analysis of neonatal sepsis isolate WGS (manuscript in preparation); KL102, KL112, KL122, KL136 and KL149 (see below). Polyclonal antisera were produced against selected reference isolates (**Supplementary Table 1**) through rabbit immunization by SSI Diagnostica, Denmark. A two-step cultivating, amplification and concentration procedure was used to prepare the *Klebsiella* vaccines for immunization of K102, K112, K122, K136 and K149. Rabbits were immunized with the vaccine in scheduled intervals. Full blood was collected and serum separated by centrifugation. The collected antisera were purified to remove unwanted components and the concentration of specific antibodies were increased. The *K. pneumoniae* K antisera were tested for serotype specificity, potency and cross-reactivity using an Internal Quality control procedure.

All strains and reference strains were tested in the new antisera and possible cross reactions were examined using absorbed sera produced at SSI, as described above.

Data analysis and visualisation

Data were summarised and visualised using R v4.5.0 [33] with the following packages: Tidyverse v2.0.0 [34], Reshape2 v1.4.4 [35] and Patchwork v1.3.0 (doi:10.32614/CRAN.package.patchwork).

Results

Isolate collection for analysis

K. pneumoniae species complex isolates were successfully recovered from 775 contributed isolate culture stocks (97.2%, species confirmed by MALDI-TOF). Among these 130 stocks yielded two or more colony morphology variants (16.8%); 98 grouped colony variants were classified as the same serotype, and only one of each group was counted in subsequent analyses; 24 groups comprised one or more serologically typeable and one non-typeable variant; and 8 groups comprised variants classified to distinct serotypes. We used *de novo* genomic sequencing to resolve colony morphology variants that yielded multiple distinct serological results, i.e. to identify the variant matching the original published WGS (ST and K locus match), which were included in subsequent analyses. Thus far we have resolved five of the 8 groups that yielded two or more distinct serotypes and 12 of the 24 groups comprising one typeable and one or more non-typeable isolates. The remaining unresolved colony morphology variant groups are excluded from the current analysis.

Following preliminary analyses, we generated additional ONT sequence data for isolates where the serological phenotype was not as expected given the K locus in the matched WGS. To-date n=28 such isolates have been sequenced, and comparison of the ONT assembly to the original Illumina assembly revealed that 14 of 28 did not match the original strain i.e. STs and/or K-loci differed from those originally reported. These mis-matching isolates have been excluded from the analyses reported here.

Serological typing

Following exclusions due to unresolved colony morphology variants and isolate mismatches, a total of 733 isolates with serotyping data were available for analysis. Six hundred and forty-one isolates (87.5%) resulted in one or more serological reactions; 560 with a single reaction (76.4% of total isolates), and 81 with multiple reactions (11.1% of total isolates). A total of 60 distinct serotypes were represented among isolates with only a single serological reaction, including 17 serotypes represented by ≥ 10 isolates each and 7 serotypes represented by ≥ 20 isolates each. The top 5 most common serotypes were K25 (n=94), K2 (n=53), K15 (n=51), K149 (n=46) and K62 (n=44).

Isolates reacting to more than one serum could be categorised into five groups (**Table 1**), and notably included reactions to four of the five novel antisera reported here (K102, K112, K122 and K136). Further investigation using the corresponding serotype reference strains indicated four pairs of phenotypes that were considered serologically identical by the reference protocol described in **Methods** (K102 and K18, K112 and K24, K122 and K35, K136 and K61), meaning that the serological reaction of the reference strain to its matched antiserum was completely inhibited by pre-absorption of the strain to the paired antiserum, and vice versa (e.g. see **Figure 1**). However, for all of these pairs of serotypes there were additional isolates in our collection that reacted to only one of the two corresponding antisera

(**Table 1**). Recent capsule structural component analyses indicate that the corresponding polysaccharide structures differ [36], and it has been shown that anticapsular antibody targeting K102 was able to bind but unable to kill a K18-producing *K. pneumoniae in vitro* (none of the other pairs were tested) [36]. We therefore consider each of K102, K112, K122, and K136 as a unique phenotype in subsequent analyses, while acknowledging that there is some level of cross-reactivity with K18, K24, K35 and K61, respectively. Importantly, further work will be needed to understand the potential for cross-protection among vaccine-induced antibodies targeting these phenotypes and others. In this study we also observed a potential cross-reaction between K149 (newly defined in this work) and K19, wherein preabsorption of the K19 reference strain with the K149 antiserum was able to inhibit a subsequent reaction with the K149 antiserum, but the reverse combination resulted in only a partial inhibition, and none of the strains serotyped as K149 reacted to the K19 antiserum.

Table 1: Isolates reacting to multiple sera and associated single reactions

Multi reaction combinations	N	Associated single reactions	N
K40 and K56	2	K40 K56	1 2
K18 and K102	45	K18 K102	0 5
K24 and K112	19	K24 K112	5 3
K35 and K122	7	K35 K122	1 0
K61 and K136	8	K61 K136	0 3

Figure 1 (overleaf): Phenotypic expression of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* capsule based on antisera and antigen precipitation. A) Immunoelectrophoresis of K extract (antigen) from K35 and K122 strains against K35 and K122 antisera. **B)** Countercurrent-immunoelectrophoresis of K extract from K35 and K122 against K35 and K122 antisera, respectively; and K35 antisera absorbed with K122 strain; and K122 antisera absorbed with K35 strain. Inhibition of the serological reaction following absorption indicates that the serotypes are considered serologically identical by the reference protocol, but does not necessarily imply that the polysaccharide structures are identical nor that antibodies targeting these structures will be cross-protective.

Genotype-phenotype comparison

Among the 733 isolates with serological typing data, 731 had WGS assemblies available, 712 of which (97.4%) passed quality control. Kaptive identified typeable K loci among 705 (99.0%) of these, and the remaining loci were marked as untypeable. Among the latter, three isolates were successfully serotyped to three distinct antisera (one each for K31, K66, K67), while four were serologically non-typeable. Untypeable Kaptive calls can result from fragmentation in the K locus region of a draft assembly or the presence of a genuine novel K locus that is not represented in the reference database [21]. We are currently in the process of generating additional WGS data to resolve these possibilities, and as such the untypeable Kaptive calls are excluded from the remaining analyses here.

Among the 705 typeable WGS, Kaptive reported 67 distinct K loci, the majority of which (n=42) were represented by ≤ 5 isolates each. However, 9 distinct K loci were each represented by >20 isolates each; KL25, KL2, KL15, KL102, KL62, KL149, KL108, KL30, KL122 (see **Figure 2, Supplementary Table 1**). We compared the Kaptive K locus calls with the matched serological phenotypes and categorised the results as expected or unexpected. Expected results were defined as; i) an isolate harbouring a K locus associated with a known serotype showed a positive reaction to the corresponding antiserum (K<100; plus novel sera for K102, K112, K122, K136, K149, noting this includes isolates that reacted to multiple

sera); or ii) an isolate harbouring a K locus that is not associated with a known serotype was non-typeable with available sera. Unexpected results were defined as either; i) an isolate harbouring a K locus associated with a known serotype (K<100, K102, K112, K136, K149) was non-typeable or reacted only with an unassociated serum; or ii) an isolate harbouring a K locus that is not associated with a known serotype showed a positive reaction to a known serum. In total, 596 (84.5%) serological typing results were as expected based on the K-loci reported by Kaptive (**Table 2**).

Table 2: Serological typing outcomes for *K. pneumoniae* with matched K locus types

	N	Serological outcome			Total expected results (%)
		+ve match	+ve mismatch	-ve	
K locus associated with known serotype	634	555	34	45	555 (87.5)
K locus NOT associated with known serotype	71	n/a	30	41	41 (57.8)
Total	476	555	64	86	596 (84.5)

Positive (+ve) and negative (-ve) serological reactions for one or more K antisera are indicated.

Positive reactions are grouped as matches (at least one of the recorded serological reactions matched that expected for the K locus) or mismatches (none of the recorded reactions matched that expected for the K locus). Grey shading indicates expected outcomes.

Figure 2 (overleaf): Serological typing outcomes for *K. pneumoniae* harbouring diverse K-loci.

A) Bubble plot showing WGS-derived K-loci (rows) and the corresponding serological reaction(s) (columns) sized and coloured as per the legend. NT indicates serologically non-typeable. **B)** Bar chart showing the total number of isolates carrying each K locus, coloured to indicate serological outcome vs genotype as per legend; 'match' indicates a positive reaction to the expected serum, with or without an additional reaction to another serum; 'mismatch' indicates positive reaction(s) only to unexpected sera; 'no reaction (expected)' indicates serologically non-typeable isolates carrying K loci that are NOT associated with a known serotype; 'no reaction (unexpected)' indicates serologically non-typeable isolates carrying K loci that are associated with a known serotype.

The unexpected results corresponded to 44 distinct K loci, and in most instances only one or two isolates were implicated. Eleven K loci were associated with three or more unexpected results each, but for seven of these the unexpected outcomes accounted for $\leq 33\%$ of isolates tested (**Table 3**). The four remaining loci included two for which there were no clear patterns among the unexpected outcomes (KL8 and KL18), plus KL108 and KL117. Three of the four tested KL117 isolates reacted to the K56 antiserum (two of these also reacted to K40), suggesting there may be some level of cross-reactivity between the polysaccharide structures synthesised by the K56 and K117 loci.

Table 3: K loci associated with ≥ 3 unexpected serological K type results

K-locus	Total N	Total unexp	Serological reactions			Sera implicated in mismatch reactions (n if >1)
			+ve match	+ve mismatch	-ve	
KL2	68	8 (12%)	60	3	5	K17, K33, K136
KL8	12	9 (75%)	3	4	5	K41, K62, K112, K136
KL17	16	4 (25%)	12	0	4	n/a
KL18	5	5 (100%)	0	1	4	K2
KL19	9	3 (33%)	6	1	2	K62
KL23	14	3 (21%)	11	1	2	K25
KL25	92	4 (<1%)	88	2	2	K12, K102
KL30	29	4 (14%)	25	2	2	K12, K15
KL62	45	3 (7%)	42	1	2	K24
KL108	35	14 (40%)	n/a	14	21	K2, K23, K24 (n=2), K39, K47 (n=2), K62, K64 (n=5), K102
KL117	4	4 (100%)	n/a	0	0	K40&K56 (n=2), K56, K64

Positive (+ve) and negative (-ve) serological reactions for one or more K sera are indicated. Positive reactions are grouped as matches (serotype matched that expected for the K-locus), mismatches (serotype did not match that expected for the K-locus). Grey shading indicates expected outcomes.

Interestingly, 14 of 35 isolates carrying KL108 (40%) unexpectedly showed positive reactions to known antisera, but the results were not consistent, with eight distinct serotypes implicated. While phase-contrast microscopy performed as part of this work indicated the presence of a capsule for all isolates, recent capsule structural investigations by our collaborators showed that 13 of the 14 isolates investigated did not produce a capsule, including three serotyped here as K64, two serotyped as K47 and one as K2 [36]. The single KL108 isolate that was shown to produce a capsule via the structural investigation did not react to any existing antisera, as expected. This raises the possibility of undetected

heterogeneity within the isolate culture stocks i.e. a mixture of capsule producing and capsule null variants, and/or differential capsule expression. We speculate that the unexpected serological reactions reported for the KL108 carrying isolates may represent non-specific binding to other surface molecules, because no capsule was produced by the colony selected for the serological test.

Capsule null mutations are expected to be rare *in vivo* among invasive infection isolates because the capsule is a major pathogenicity determinant required for invasive disease [37]. In contrast, such mutations are known to occur frequently during culture in rich media [38]. Interestingly, all of the KL108 isolates included in this work were collected from the same country and all but two differed by <15 pairwise single nucleotide variants in 1972 core genes (the remaining two differed by up to 24 variants), suggesting they represent a locally transmitting clone. We therefore speculate that this clone may be associated with an uncommon capsule regulatory phenotype and/or an unusually high risk of capsule null mutation, although we have not yet been able to identify any known capsule null conferring mutations in any of the corresponding K loci. Hence, we cannot rule out the possibility that the capsule null mutation or some sort of capsule regulatory defect was acquired and disseminated in the hospital setting. The latter scenario warrants further investigation because it has major implications for the efficacy of vaccines targeting the *Kp* polysaccharide capsule.

Forty-five additional isolates were non-typeable by serology and carried K loci associated with known sera (n=24 distinct sera, **Figure 2, Supplementary Table 1**). Kaptive reported capsule assembly and export protein truncations that likely explain three of these (truncated WcaJ, initiating glycosyltransferase [29]) and further investigations are underway to identify any additional contributing variations. These may include protein truncations resulting from insertion sequence insertions that cause assembly fragmentation and which will not be reported by Kaptive. (Kaptive takes a conservative approach, reporting protein truncations only when the corresponding gene nucleotide sequence is contiguous in the assembly i.e. where we can be confident that the truncation is not due to assembly artefacts [21]).

Kaptive also reported capsule assembly and export protein truncations that are thought to result in capsule null phenotypes but for which the corresponding isolates showed positive reactions to known sera (n=11 matches, n=3 mismatches). The associated truncations were reported for n=5 Wzx (flippase), n=4 WcaJ and n=1 WbaP (initiating glycosyltransferases), n=2 Wzc (tyrosine autokinase, regulator of polysaccharide polymerisation), n=1 each of Wzb (phosphorylates Wzc) and Wzy (repeat unit polymerase) [39]. It is possible that these mutations occurred during culture for DNA extraction and/or that the original stock contained sub-populations with and without the mutations which were inadvertently used for DNA extraction and serological typing, respectively. It is also possible that these findings reflect gaps in our knowledge, for example while we are not aware of any reports to-date for *K. pneumoniae*, in *Acinetobacter baumannii* it is known that Wzy orthologs outside of the K locus can contribute to capsule production [40]. Further investigations into the associated isolate WGS are ongoing, including resequencing of isolate stocks at SSI.

Conclusions

Our data suggest that Kaptive v3 predicts *K. pneumoniae* serological K types with high accuracy (>84%), supporting its use in genomics-based sero-epidemiology analyses to inform the design of *K. pneumoniae* control strategies targeting the capsule. Work is ongoing to expand the dataset to additional isolates from different geographies and to confirm the genotype-phenotype discrepancies. KpSC K-loci are often fragmented in draft WGS assemblies because the capsule-specific genes are subject to GC-dependent sequencing drop-out during Illumina sequencing, in particular when the Nextera XT library preparation is used [21]. In order to resolve this issue, we plan to generate completed WGS for a subset of isolates using *de novo* ONT sequencing (in progress). The resulting assemblies will be used to further investigate genotype-phenotype discrepancies and identify additional genetic variations that impact serotype. Where appropriate, this information will be incorporated into Kaptive to further improve its accuracy.

Data Availability Statement

Serological typing data and Kaptive genotyping information are available in **Supplementary Table 1**. Illumina WGS data for the BARNARDS and MLW collections are available via the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA), under the individual accessions listed in **Supplementary Table 1**. Illumina WGS data for the SA-WITS-VIDA collection will be available via ENA following acceptance of the primary publication describing these data [28].

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